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“Defining and Analyzing Community Violence in their Community: Jane-Finch Youth Perception of Violence in their Toronto Community”ⁱ

by S. Nombuso Dlamini, Uzo Anucha & Alex Lovell

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Abstract

This paper discusses findings from a larger research study entitled Assets Coming Together for Youth: ACT (2009 – 2015) that focused on the Jane-Finch neighbourhood, a stigmatized urban environment located in the North York region of Toronto, Ontario, Canada. Underpinned by research on urban youth violence and on community characteristics, social capital, and street context, this paper presents the viewpoints of youth from the Jane-Finch community on issues of violence and turf. Data collected by and from youth using a novel qualitative methodology called the Mobile Speakers’ Corner (MSC) investigated (a) how youth identify violence and its causes, (b) how they experience and respond to violence, and (c) the solutions they offer to combat violence in their community. Our findings suggested that youth participants have a comprehensive understanding of what constitutes violence. In addition, the data revealed multiple ways youth have of dealing with the violence in their everyday lives as well as their strategies to combat the violence they see in their community.

Keywords: youth and communities; youth voices; violence; disenfranchised communities; prioritized neighbourhoods; youth studies.

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Over the past two decades, there have been scholarly articles that have documented and theorized on the nature of violence from the point of view of youth who may have encountered and/or committed violent acts themselves. Our paper builds on these articles, specifically on those that draw upon positive youth development theory to unpack youth perspectives on violence (see, for example, Daiute & Fine, 2003). This framework, rather than promulgating the traditional notion of youth as deviants and problems to be managed, presents youth as assets with possibilities (Forman 2004; Ginwright & Cammarotta, 2002), as sources of knowledge and power (Fox, Mediratta, & Ruglis, 2010), and as agents of social change (Putnam, 1995) with competencies to critically examine the world around them and their participation in it (Giddens, 1984).

Following this framework, coupled with our community-partner-knowledge base, this paper presents results from sections of data of a larger study, *Assets Coming Together for Youth* (Anucha et al, 2009-2015), conducted with young people from the Jane-Finch area in Toronto, Canada. Funded in 2009, *Assets Coming Together for Youth* (ACT for Youth) had an overall goal to examine the ways that community assets (e.g. people, resources, etc.) can work together to enhance the lives of youth and be used to create meaningful future possibilities. *ACT for Youth* had five interconnected working groups that are each designed to investigate a specific themeⁱⁱ. The data presented here is drawn from the summer 2010 research explorations of the Youth Voices Working Group (YVWG).

Two major roads, Jane Street and Finch Avenue, intersect in the north-western corner of Toronto. The neighborhood around this intersection, known by Canadians as Jane-Finch, is home to over 80,000 people of diverse racial, ethnic, religious and generational backgrounds (City of Toronto, 2008). Although not usually referred to as such, Jane-Finch is part of the Black Creek

area of which York University is located (see appendix 1). With a high population density, a high concentration of racial and ethnic minorities, low-income housing, gangs, drug problems and violence Jane-Finch is often viewed as a Canadian equivalent to an American ghetto (O'Grady, Parnaby & Schickschneit, 2010 and James, 2012). It is considered the most gang concentration area in all of Canada,

http://www.thestar.com/news/crime/2013/08/31/jane_and_finch_torontos_most_dangerous_place_to_be_a_kid.html and is repeatedly portrayed as an incubator of trouble and violence that offers youth a limited perspective of the opportunities they can gain in life. Media coverage has reinforced this negative image of Jane-Finch as a “troubled” community. “Even as the media attempt to present ‘positive’ portraits of the community, or ‘look deeper’ into it, they often reinforce the very ideas they claim to want to counteract” (James, 2012, p. 36).

The Jane-Finch area has been subjected to loads of institutional research; thus, as researchers, we moved cautiously because of awareness that Jane-Finch residents had become somewhat ambivalent and suspicious of ‘outsiders’ who do research on them. Our approach then was multifaceted and aimed at conducting activities leading to youth engagement, capacity building and economic practicalities; that is, while our focus was on hearing youth voices on community issues, we also wanted to positively engage youth socially and economically.

The youth whose ideas we present herein, were part of ACT for Youth’s - Youth Voices Working Group (YVWG), which engaged youth by designing sub-projects that aimed to uncover their viewpoints on three themes: wellbeing, violence, and turf issuesⁱⁱⁱ. Specifically, the YVWG asked the questions: What are the perspectives of youth concerning their needs and wellbeing? How do youth understand “turf issues” in their community?^{iv} How do youth experience violence in their lives? This paper presents youth ideas on these questions, which in turn, we hoped would allow youth to think more broadly about community activities and their participation in them.

Understanding Communities and Violence

Studies on urban violence have posited that there is a relationship between community characteristics and youth violence, a suggestion that has laid the foundation for the commonly held belief among police (and the general public) that crime occurs in particular areas (disadvantaged neighbourhoods) and among particular people (lower class, ethnic/racial minorities) (Alvi, 2000; Ezeonu, 2010; Rennison & Melde, 2009; Symons, 1999). Building on this neighborhood disadvantage approach, other studies have added two other perspectives – social capital and street context – to examine the mechanism and effects of community disadvantage on violence (De Coster, Heimer & Wittrock, 2006).

Community Characteristics

The literature suggests that residential patterns are constrained by individual and family characteristics where race, income, and head of family are a major factor. Within this literature, interpersonal violence is said to be concentrated in neighbourhoods characterized by poverty, racial segregation, and a high number of single-parent families, many of which are headed by women (see, for example, Sabol, Coulton, & Korbin, 2004). This literature refers to these communities as ‘constrained residential’ spaces where many minority groups live and where family income is a crucial determining factor for residential patterns of settlement (Bursik & Grasmick, 1993). Some literature suggests that this minority residential location situation is maintained through discriminatory practices that discourage minority families who manage to climb the economic ladder from transitioning into advantaged community locations. Some scholars argue that White adults engage in processes (for instance, subtle deterrents from real estate agents and bank practices) that help protect ‘their’ advantaged territories (Massey and Fong, 1990; South and Deanne, 1993; Hagedorn 2005).

This spatial separation of the affluent from the poor “has been supplemented by the adoption of ‘tough on crime’ policies, despite the falling violent crime rates in the 1990s” (Hagedorn, 2005, p. 162). These policies, primarily aimed at socially isolated, unemployed African American youth, have led to an undue emphasis on establishing correction facilities that incarcerate a disproportionate number of this marginalized population (Hagedorn, 2005; Grekul & La-Boucane-Benson, 2008; Reiman, 2007). In general, the literature theorizes that status characteristics of individual families are what determine residential choices, suggesting furthermore that impoverished and black families are most likely to reside in disadvantaged areas.

Social Capital

Social capital, defined as the “set of norms and organizations through which people gain access to power and resources and through which decision-making and policy formulation occur” (Seragelding & Grootaert, 1998, p. 2) has also been found to affect the level of violence in communities. Because social capital is about the features of social organization including norms, and the trust that facilitates cooperation for mutual benefit (Putnam, 1995), the theory is that communities where residents are interconnected are able to work together to prevent an outbreak of crime and violence. Indeed, an impressive body of literature confirms the effects of social capital on the domains of the economy, politics, social structure, education, social control, crime, inter-group relations, social mobility, lifestyles, and health of a neighbourhood. Schriver (2001) suggests that the concept of social capital offers an opportunity to understand aspects of human behaviour at the individual, family, group, organizational, community and societal levels.

Yet despite the impressive and positive results associated with this concept, there is growing recognition that there are downsides to the processes that build and maintain it (Coleman, 1988; Saegert, Winkel and Swartz, 2002). These downsides include: (a) practices where groups use their social capital to exclude others and to deny them opportunities that enhance social

mobility, which in turn contributes to intergenerational inequalities, and (b) the negative social capital found in certain social networks such as inner-city youth gangs and organized-crime-families. Bursik (1999) suggests that the absence of social capital results in a failure to establish social norms and values, which could deter violence. Other literature disputes this view, arguing that many poor communities do have very strong family and community networks, which nevertheless fail to produce needed resources to deter violence (Wilson, 1996; Reiman, 2007; Sheldon, Tracy, & Brown, 2004). Pattillo-McCoy (1999) argues that the existence of strong networks in disadvantaged communities may themselves generate negative activities such as drug dealing. Some urban studies scholars have gone so far as to argue that such strong ties are not necessarily that important and are no longer the norm in metropolitan areas, and that the political and economic organizing necessary for the urban spaces to function does not necessarily depend on friendship and traditional community networks (Amin & Thrift, 2002).

Street Context

Street context is a concept proposed by Anderson's (1997) research, and in line with the importance of the social capital framework, it posits that there exists a role between families and communities in mediating violence. Anderson refers to the responsibility of what he calls "decent" families to protect their children from the violence and crime in their homes and community. Ultimately, however, even children who come from decent families eventually learn the realities of the street. To Anderson, the structural problems of the inner city produce a street context where violence becomes part and parcel of everyday life. Children grow up witnessing the violence perpetrated by adults in public; others experience violence at the hands of adults in private, which in turn creates in them a sense of hopelessness as well as diminishing a sense of a meaningful future.

In the rest of the article, we draw from the literature on community characteristics, social capital, and street context to understand the voices of youth who participated in our ACT for Youth study. In terms of community characteristics, there is ample evidence that the Jane-Finch community is a jarring example of Canada's growing income polarization, which, coupled with concentrated and racialized patterns of poverty, has resulted in socioeconomic inequity. The reasons for this polarization are complex. For instance, it has been suggested that it stems in part from decades of chronic underinvestment in physical and social infrastructure (Cowen & Parlette, 2011), coupled with the speed and depth of population changes, a shifting immigration policy, and pervasive racism in local labour and housing markets.

According to a broadcast by the *Fifth Estate* (2006), the Jane-Finch neighborhood population expanded by more than 200% between 1960 and 1970; however, the infrastructure in the community failed to support the needs of these newcomers who became overwhelmed by a lack of public transportation, scarce social services, and high rates of unemployment. During this period of rapid increase in population coupled with a failing infrastructure, the community gained notoriety for its low-income, high-crime status, eventually being named one of the city's 13 priority neighborhoods (United Way, 2011). Priority neighborhoods are areas that have been identified by the city of Toronto as generally experiencing a population loss; have a higher than average number of at-risk populations: visible minorities, recent immigrants; lone-parent families; incomes that are generally below the city average, and with unemployment rates for the population 15+ higher than the city average (City of Toronto, 2006). The negative perception of Jane-Finch prevailed in the media until the 1970s when the community came together to reframe its image by focusing on its assets. In 2004, community activist Paul Nguyen launched Jane-Finch.com, a community website to act as a hub for community members and that aims to "...create a better understanding and appreciation of the Jane-Finch community by sharing its cultural and historical

beauty” (Nguyen, 2011). ACT for Youth has paid tribute to Nguyen’s aim by using a positive youth development approach and by engaging various stakeholders working with youth in the community.

Methodology

Methodological Framing

We collected our data through a qualitative method termed the Mobile Speakers’ Corner (MSC), which consisted of mobile audio set-ups in each of the two malls that serve the Jane-Finch area. This method entailed giving each participant a tape recorder and some questions that asked them to talk about their perception of violence in their community. The MSC framework builds on the work of scholars who wished to avoid the speculative theorizing resulting from the limitations of quantitative methods (official data, self-report surveys, victimization surveys) and therefore adopted a more qualitative approach to youth crime and community violence (Bjerregaard & Lizotte, 1995; Decker & Van Winkle, 1996; Ezeonu, 2010; Fagan, 1989; Grekul & La-Boucane-Benson, 2008; Gordon et al., 2004; Maclure & Sotelo, 2004; Nakhid, 2009; Symons, 1999; Venkatesh, 2008). While these studies are often criticized for their small sample sizes and thus their non-generalizability, the in-depth interviews and ethnographic research that are their features have been commended for their ability to shed light on particular aspects of the youth gang phenomenon and community violence that are otherwise unavailable in survey research or in the analysis of official data. Importantly for us, by using this framework, we could engage youth not only in describing and discussing their experiences but also in the forward-looking task of re-conceptualizing violence in ways that could meaningfully capture their concerns and needs.

In addition to seeking to create venues for youth to tell their stories and to offer their perspectives on community violence, the broader ACT for Youth project (which the MSC was part

of) also aimed to educate and empower youth by (a) encouraging their active participation in developing youth-sector violence-prevention tools, and (b) creating opportunities within the research project for the participants to acquire and enhance their own skills. In the end, fifty youth participated in the MSC (see appendix for demographic details). Determined through the use of their postal codes, these youth were from the main ethno-racial groups in the community; however, the profile of the respondents was not as diverse as the youth profile of Jane-Finch where there are families from over eighty countries and where there are more than a hundred languages spoken.

Data Collection Sites

We chose to set up in these two malls for three strategic reasons. First, in addition to having many stores commonly frequented by youth, both malls also provide youth-centred drop in places (coffee shops, internet cafes) that would give us easy access to prospective participants.

Furthermore, in one of the malls is a community centre called “The Spot,” which is popular for its positive social engagement of youth and which had previously partnered with the ACT for Youth project during its formation; this mall also houses York University’s TD Centre for Community Engagement, which offers various social and academic programs. Consequently, we anticipated relatively easy access to the Jane-Finch youth visiting these malls.

Our second reason for choosing these malls was because of the blandness that such spaces typically provide because of their large open spaces and mass movement of people.

Lastly, as researchers, our own knowledge of the facilities and layout of these malls made them an attractive site for recruiting youth participants. For example, over the years, Dlamini has taught an urban education course where one of the assignments has students engaging in a psycho-geography exploration of an urban space of their choice. The students who chose these malls documented a continuous youth presence even during ‘senior citizen time,’ that is, the time when

youngsters are typically in schools. Such information indicated to us that regardless of the time and day of data collection, there would be youth around whom we could invite to participate in the study.

Research Assistant Training

The selection of youth researchers (YR) was purposive (Gall, Borg, & Gall, 1996; Ristock & Grieger, 1996), focusing on youngsters aged 18–24 who were enrolled in high schools, colleges, or universities and who were socio-politically informed about the Jane-Finch neighbourhood itself. The YR – two Indo-Canadians, two Caribbean Canadians, and one white Canadian – were employed to work in the MSC and in other broader ACT for Youth data collection initiatives.

Their first activity was learning how to interview. At this stage, the YR worked with a faculty member for about 15 hours to learn how to conduct qualitative research. Training topics included research ethics, interviewing strategies, how to generate probing questions, and how to transcribe audio-recorded interviews.

For the second part of their training, the YR conducted a 15–20 minute interview with a non-YR youth who had something interesting to say about violence in their community. The interview transcripts and reflection sheets were used to provide feedback to the YR to improve their skills. Reflection sheets indicated that the training enhanced the YR's understanding of qualitative research ethics, taught them critical skills that they could use to look at their environment and the context of their interviewing, and empowered them to work with their peers.

Ethics

The York University research ethics board approved our project. Because of Jane-Finch's reputation as a haven for criminalized youth, we wanted to ensure that we could honour our

promise of confidentiality to the participating youth. Accordingly, in our ethics application, we specified that youth living in the area would be excluded from conducting interviews and from engaging in the MSC initiative to avoid the possibility of a YR making a link between the research data and a specific research subject. To further preserve anonymity, each participant at the outset of the project was asked to choose a pseudonym and to use it throughout the recording. All records were stored in our university research office without any identifying markers.

Data Collection Process

Data collection in the malls was carried out as follows:

- (a) Youth researchers (YR) set up tables at the entrance of the mall containing their research tools festooning them with ACT for Youth banners large enough to attract attention.
- (b) When a young person entered the mall, the YR approached and told them about the study, went over the research ethics forms, and invited them to participate.
- (c) If the person was interested, the YR then obtained consent from the participant, the YR gave them a tape recorder plus a paper with the research questions. The YR then asked demographics questions, explained how to use the tape recorder, and explained that the participant had to respond to only one of the three research questions. Each of the three questions contained subquestions designed to guide (or in a typical face-to-face interview, probe) the participant into thinking more deeply about the question.
- (d) Finally, tape recorder and question sheet in hand, the recruited participant would find a spot with sight but not hearing of the YR, talk on tape for about five minutes (thus, the mobile tape termed MSC), return the tape recorder and collect his/her \$10 honorarium.

The recordings were then transcribed by the YR verbatim, entered into Nvivo, a qualitative software program, and analyzed using thematic analysis techniques (Boyatzis, 1998). We used an

iterative process of identifying and organizing emerging themes to analyze the data, focusing on how participants' narratives produced, troubled, or disrupted the notion of Jane-Finch youth as troublemakers with limited understanding of the world around them. In all stages of the analysis, the graduate assistants who worked on the project were present to document the interpretations, which were later incorporated into and aligned with themes that had emerged in previous ACT for Youth subprojects. Data were coded, using words that had been extracted from the transcripts. The codes were then grouped into concepts and categories, which made up the final themes.

Methodological Challenges

Our qualitative methodology had both advantages and limitations. With its high level of anonymity, the MSC allowed for diverse youth voices, giving us access to youth who could talk about turf issues and the violence in their community without fear of being rebuked and/or identified. No names appeared on the tapes and transcripts, which meant that no one could be linked to a particular recording, thus encouraging the participants to talk about violence as part and parcel of their lives, including the whys and hows of their participation in or commission of violent acts.

On the other hand, this anonymity meant that we could not return to participants to ask for clarification of or elaboration on some of the statements they had made on these issues; consequently, we were sometimes left with 'hanging ideas,' that is, ideas that would warrant further discussion and further information if participant-checking had been an option. Finally, we came to realize the complexity of the language used by this group of youth and of our ignorance of its subtleties and idiosyncrasies. When transcribed, some of the information in the transcripts was incomprehensible to us primarily because the words and phrases used were more than just slang and needed a particular context and background, which we lacked, to make them meaningful. To

address this challenge, we relied on our community partners (e.g. “The Spot”) who work directly with youth to either help with meaning-making or to find young people to interpret these words and phrases^v. None of these partners should be blamed for flaws in interpretation.

Findings

We grouped the MSC data into three categories: (a) identifying violence and its causes; (b) the experiences of and responses to violence; and, (c) identifying solutions to violence.

Identifying Violence and Its Causes

Youth in our study identified violence as bullying, guns, gangs, crime, racial discrimination, and street and domestic viciousness. Some of the indicators of this violence included bullying, shooting, assault, drugs, racism/racial stigma, street fights, and physical cruelty at home. Notably, youth identified various forms of violence while simultaneously talking about its causes to the point where it became difficult to differentiate the cause of the violence from the violence itself, and we questioned whether it was possible or even advisable to separate cause and action.

For instance, twelve out of the fifty participants identified racial discrimination as violence; however, it was unclear from the data whether this discrimination was the precursor to the violence or the violence was a response to the discrimination. These youth also spoke of race and ethnic background in ways that suggested that the cause of the violence they experienced in Jane-Finch was intertwined with their identity as racial minorities.

There is a lot of discrimination, like people get bullied [because of] where they are from. If they are from India or Pakistan, people are just running around and talking about terrorists and all that stupid stuff. It really hurts other people when people say these things. [For

example,] if you are Asian, they say that you can't see, or always talking about Chinese food. It's messed up in this way. That is the violence I see. There is a lot of discrimination and all that.

I want to start by saying that my best friend has been killed by police brutality.... Thirty one [police] division is my main problem. I don't like how they operate, I don't like how they profile people and put us into categories [of blackness] as if we were bad, and the real bad people actually get to get away and do whatever they are doing. So my main problem with Jane-Finch community is not the community itself; it's the actual police officers who think that they control the people in the community...

Three other elements identified as roots of violence were lack of opportunities to access post-secondary education, lack of recreational spaces, and lack of positive role models, all of which served to narrow the respondents' sense of positive and meaningful economic and social engagement.

Many of the kids living around this area have very few chances of accessing higher education or post-secondary education and they do not know much English so most of the time...they mix with the wrong friends and the friends just drag them to do anything that...anything that is illegal for them.

There's a lack of role models in the community [...] Youth are feeling a lack of motivation. They don't have anybody to guide them because they are stranded, as well. So I feel that is also a factor influencing youth to turn to violence

Experiences of and Responses to Violence

The data indicated that Jane-Finch youth are exposed to diverse forms of violence in their everyday lives. Twenty-seven of the fifty participants spoke of being either victims of violence or involved in it, and all of them discussed typical methods they use to respond to this violence.

The single most identified experience with violence cited by youth was racial discrimination, which we coded using the words “discrimination,” “stereotype,” “racism,” and “stigma.” Anyone who used one or more of these words to refer to their experiences with violence was categorized being subject to the violence of discrimination. Of the twenty-seven youth who mentioned being discriminated against, twelve specifically identified racial discrimination as part of their daily encounters with the general public, the media, and the police, as indicated by the following three quotes:

[The general public] One of the sources of the violence that I’ve experienced has been, I would say, discrimination, in a sense that you know people automatically...they see you as a black young person, and they feel that...you know, you being black, you would never amount to nothing, you’re never going to be nothing good, but that’s not always true.

[The media] Especially knowing that the media makes our community show that we are bad and that we have issues.

[The police] The police don't even do nothing when it comes to violence, I think they [...] make violence build more because they don't even help; they interrogate and stuff and they intimidate.

In addition to the violence of racial discrimination, youth referred to experiences of physical violence, which were coded using the words “robbed,” “street fights,” and “shootings/death.” Shootings leading to death were the most noted experience mentioned by six of the eleven youth who referred to physical violence. The following two quotes are illustrative:

People that are close to me have passed away for nonsense because of gun violence....

But in Jane-Finch, it went to the next level, such as after school being called to a secluded area where there would be a gang war. [...] I was there to help one of my friends who was in trouble. I didn't know he was part of this gang. So the violent aspect of it would be that there didn't seem to be an end to the argument in the debate, and eventually it escalated to more of a contact in a violent way.

The last form of violence mentioned was domestic violence:

In my life, my mom has been beaten in front of me; she's been abused. My father kicked her, punched her, all that kind of stuff when [we] were children. He believes he can do this; he believes that we as children, that is, my brother and I, did not notice, did not care, and we were just little kids that were stupid ignorant and just didn't know anything about the world and we do not remember it [the abuse of the mother].

Data from the study indicated that youth came up with multiple ways to respond to the violence in their lives and in the community. Some believed in the notion that “if you go somewhere, you

mind your own business, you'll be fine." Others spoke about protecting themselves: "I don't care about the violence because it doesn't come around me anymore because they know not to mess with me. They know I am not somebody to play around with."

Some youth lived in fear: "[Violence] impacts the lives close to me because they get shot and then they are afraid to come outside," while others resigned themselves to the inevitability of violence: "People are killing each other and all that, but you can't have a good with no bad."

Still others believed in avoiding violence by staying at home, using the strategy of staying away from 'wrong' people because "you have a better chance of being saved if you are not into gangs and drugs," and others simply moved elsewhere: "My mom has moved a couple of times when my brother was involved and stuff and when stuff would happen in the community, but she also tended to move back [to Jane-Finch]."

And finally, there were some who believed in speaking out – to acquaintances, to the police, to members of the community – when they experienced or witnessed violence:

What have I, what I have done for others affected by violence? Mmm... Honestly, I just helped them and it's good to talk about things, better than to hold them in. Like, for instance, my brother's best friend passed away.... [My brother] was very depressed and I chose to talk to him about it even though he didn't want to.

Identifying Solutions to Violence

When asked about their ideas for stopping or dealing with violence, participants made five suggestions. The first two were about providing opportunities and recreational spaces:

There's a lack of employment. There's a lack of opportunities for education. I just feel that if these social issues were addressed more properly, there would be fewer chances or less risk of youth being involved in violent situations.

The way violence can be addressed in Jane and Finch is by having more programs, more fun programs that help them stay out of violence.

Others believed that solutions lie within the community; for them, not only is the law (referred to as the police) incapable of addressing the violence, but exposure to bad models exacerbates the problem. Accordingly, some youth suggested legislation banning guns in the community. Another suggestion was to provide youth with positive role models:

I think that you can just try to sit and talk to the older people, the older adults who lived through the violence and have changed their life around and talk to the youth and try to help the youth, try to help the community to be a better place.

Over half of the participants (29 of 50) were aware of how the prevailing socioeconomic structure constrained opportunities for youth. They pointed to poor maintenance of public housing buildings and to inadequate educational, employment, and recreational opportunities as some of the conditions creating stress and leading to domestic and street violence.

I've noticed that around the Jane-Finch community, there are not a lot of resources. As you know, Jane-Finch is really big community. All we have is one public swimming pool, you know. I don't see any camping or programs for young kids, young adults –

you know, stuff for them to do. That's why they have nothing else to do than to get into drugs, alcohol, violence, because they don't have a recreation centre where they can go hang out, get help with homework, talk about issues, have somewhere to hang around, then have something to do.

Discussion

The Mobile Speakers' Corner (MSC) data confirmed results from other studies that suggest that youth are not only capable of dissecting their communities but may also see the problems and challenges inherent in them (Daiute & Fine, 2003). Our data also indicated that Jane-Finch youth are able to offer more nuanced definitions of what violence is; that is, they were able to identify violence beyond its typical physical manifestations (guns, murder, street fights), pinpointing discrimination and lack of opportunities, including barriers to post-secondary schooling, as two major forms of violence in their lives.

Lack of opportunities was repeatedly cited in our study as a barrier to youth engagement. We see this phenomenon, especially the lack of opportunities for successful schooling as the "violence of low expectations"^{vi}. Youth, in fact, often cited that their teachers did not necessarily care whether or not they applied themselves in their studies or that the teachers seemed removed from and/or uninterested in the socioeconomic challenges that youth faced that made schooling difficult for them.

These data, however, conflict with City of Toronto findings that analyzed Jane-Finch students' educational achievements. For instance, in 2005, the Jane-Finch area had the highest number of youth without a secondary school diploma in Toronto; however, the numbers have changed significantly in recent years. In fact, in 2012, only two of the ten federal census tracts with

the highest percentage (> 30%) of 20- to 24-year-olds without a secondary school diploma were in priority and disadvantage communities – and Jane-Finch was not one of them (Lovell, 2012).

This contradiction in the data can have several meanings. First, it may mean that even though Jane-Finch youth are experiencing improvements in school achievement, the quantitative rise does not match the self-perceived quality of their learning experiences. Second, it is possible that the differences in data stem from different meanings assigned to the word ‘achievement,’ a term that is linked to expectations. That is, while youth are quantitatively achieving more than before, they now have higher goals for themselves that are not in line with the standards used in analyzing the quantitative data.

Regardless of the meaning of ‘achievement,’ our finding is important because it confirms the role that race and culture play together in producing problematic learning experiences, which, in ACT for Youth, youth identified as a form of violence.

How youth responded to violence depended partly on the kind of violence in question as well as its pervasiveness. Our data indicated that youth who referred to the violence of racial discrimination seemed resigned to it. In fact, those who experienced discrimination at school and in the streets often did not answer the questions about what they do when experiencing or witnessing violence and what they thought the solution(s) should be. On the other hand, those who talked about experiencing physical violence had multiple strategies for dealing with it, including staying at home, minding their own business, protecting themselves, and moving to live in another area, even if only temporarily.

Our data are in line with studies claiming that ‘neighbourhoodism’ – that is, discrimination based on where one lives – can lead to self-paralysis, or the inability to challenge and change one’s station in life. Jackson et al. (2003) explain that the negative and stigmatizing portrayals of low-income neighborhoods can affect residents in the following ways:

(i) Community members internalize such information and describe themselves in negative or problem-based terms; (ii) community workers and agencies come into communities to ‘fix’ problems that workers have identified and offer training to community members on how to fix problems; and (iii) communities are denied opportunities for growth and development because of how labels lead others to perceive their communities (pp. 339– 340).

Conclusion and Youth Solutions

The MSC data also indicated the existence of what Meyer (2003) calls minority stress, which is the “excess stress to which individuals from stigmatized social categories are exposed to as a result of their social, often a minority, position” (Meyer, 2003, p. 675). Minority stress contributes to the internalization of social exclusion, harassment, violence, systemic discrimination, and internalized oppression (Meyer, 2003, p. 680). Thus, we conclude that an analysis that is informed by *intersectionality theory*, which is a theory that examines how identity is governed by the experience of social oppression or privilege (Crenshaw, 1991; Delgado, 1995; Palmer et al, 2010), is essential to demonstrate an understanding for how the racialization of youth gets them involved in gangs and violence in the Canadian context.

Social capital studies including ACT for Youth are meaningful for explaining young people’s perception of their disenfranchisement, which underlines their repeated demands for positive role models to counter their overexposure to adults whose visible networks they reject. Nor do they want the next generation to contend with their own experience of streets marked by different forms of violence, policed by what they perceive as biased police officers, and used by media and politicians alike to create news and gain votes, respectively.

ACT for Youth provides extensive documentation of the experiences of well-being, community, and violence of youth living in Jane-Finch that challenge narratives that (a) explain young people's success as being merely the result of individual effort, and (b) negatively portray the community to which these youth belong. Youth identified for themselves and recommended a dire need for positive role models, an education system that cares for and caters for their needs, political action that moves beyond the 'voter securing syndrome' and, importantly, local and committed initiatives that work to empower and critically engage youth voices. Therefore, as we continue to work with the youth of Jane-Finch, we are cognizant of and have faith in their ability to identify and configure remedies to the violence in their community and to turn this knowledge into workable solutions.

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Mobile Speakers’ Corner Socio-demographics

Socio-demographic Characteristics		Number	Percent
Age Groups	Less than 15	1	2%
	15 to 19	23	46%
	19 to 25	17	34%
	25 and Over	9	18%
Gender	Female	21	42%
	Male	29	58%
Race¹	Black	28	56%
	East Asian	8	16%
	First Nation	1	2%
	Latin American	4	8%
	Multi-racial	2	4%
	South Asian	3	6%
	White	2	4%
	Not Answered	2	4%
Born Outside of Canada	No	12	24%
Length of Residence in Jane-Finch	Less than 2 Years	4	8%
	2-5 Years	9	18%
	5-10 Years	6	12%
	More than 10 Years	29	58%
	Not Answered	2	4%
Total		50	100%

Reference Map of Jane-Finch, Toronto

Endnotes

ⁱ Funding for the original ACT for Youth study was provided by the Social Sciences Humanities Research Council under the call referred to as the Community University Research Alliance (SSHRC-CURA).

ⁱⁱ The working groups are: (a) Youth Voices, which was designed to investigate youth perspectives on violence, well-being, and turf issues; (b) Youth Survey, which designed a survey to create an asset profile of youth in Jane-Finch; (c) Youth Education and Employment Strategies, which aimed at understanding youth-focused pathways to successful improvement in employment; (d) Reframing Discourse through a Strategic Frame Analysis of media and documents, which aimed at understanding how communities can reframe the negative public discourse about youth to a public discourse that is supportive of positive youth development policies; and, (e) Evaluation and Monitoring theme, which aimed at developing an empowerment evaluation framework to address ways that researchers can build a sustainable, equitable community-university research partnership.

ⁱⁱⁱ In the summer of 2010, the YVWG conducted two projects: the Mobile Speakers' Corner (MSC) and the Photo-Voice (PV) project. In the PV project youth took images that captured their understanding of and experiences with community wellbeing. Additionally, youth engaged in critical dialogue about their community and structural determinants that affect their individual wellbeing in focus groups..

^{iv} This question can be asked in different ways: How do youth understand what community they 'rep'? Do they have a 'hood pass'? Community partners who work to provide youth-friendly community centres were instrumental in the construction of the questions and in making the language youth-centred.

^v A good example can be drawn from one transcript where one youth, talking about the way violence impacted those close to him, said, "Well, I am in a PAKS community in terms of giving it a bad record and all that, plus blue." During data analysis, we were initially at loss about the meaning of "PAKS" and "plus blue," but with the help of our youth partners, we learnt that "PAKS" refers to one of the gangs and that "plus blue" refers to a category of danger, different colors being used to indicate how dangerous a gang is. Ironically, in this categorization, there are actually "good" gangs, which explains the notion of "bad record" mentioned by the participant.

^{vi} This phrase appears in one article used earlier in the study; however, we have been unable to locate the author or the article itself.